

Studies in Thiadiazoles. Part V. Synthesis of some New 1,3-Di-substituted Ureas, Sulphonylureas, and Related Compounds

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Several substituted thiadiazolylureas, sulphonylureas, and sulphonylhydantoina have been prepared with a view to studying their biological properties.

A variety of substituted ureas or the compounds having the essential features of a urea structure are known to display interesting biological properties, e.g. acylureas show sedative and hypnotic activities¹, uroides and hydantoina exhibit anticonvulsant properties², and arylsulphonylureas like Tolbutamide, Chlorpropamide, and Carbutamide are well-known hypoglycemic compounds. Recently Holan *et al.*³ have reported marked hypoglycemic activity in a variety of sulphonylhydantoina.

Thioureas are apparently equally versatile as is evident from their use as bacteriostatic³⁻⁴, pesticidal⁵, and tuberculostatic⁶ agents. Sulphanilylthiourea has been shown to have excellent antimycotic, antibacterial, and antitubercular action⁷.

In view of the above and guided by the fact that a thiadiazole nucleus contains a thiourea residue, it has been considered that a combination of such a moiety with a urea (I), a sulphonylurea (II), and a hydantoin structure(III) may yield compounds of enhanced biological activities. Further, with the exception of the isolated records that 2-sulphanil-amido-5-isopropylthiadiazole has hypoglycemic activity⁸ and that certain bis-(alkylthiadiazol)-2-yl-ureas have been prepared as possible hypoglycemic agents⁹, no systematic study of analogous thiadiazole derivatives has apparently been undertaken so far.

(I)

(II)

1. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", 2nd ed., pp. 372, 370-380.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4660.
3. Beaver *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1238.
4. Bun-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2815.
5. Frear, "Chemistry of Pesticides", 2nd ed., p. 65.
6. Burger, Ref. No 1, p. 880.
7. Kurzer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, 50, 2.
8. Burger, Ref. No. 1, p. 808.
9. Cortese and Ermili, *Farmaco. Ed. Sci.*, 1964, 19, 218.

1,3-Bis-(5'-aryl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)ureas were prepared by heating together a mixture of urea and hydrochloride salt of 2-amino-5-aryl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole¹⁰. 1-(5'-Aryl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-yl)-3-arylureas were obtained by reacting an appropriate arylurea with the hydrochloride salt of the requisite aminothiadiazole.

(III)

Arylsulphonylureas were prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of an appropriate arylsulphonamide with potassium cyanate¹¹. These, when condensed with the hydrochlorides of the appropriate aminothiadiazoles, furnished 1-substituted thiadiazolyl-3-arylsulphonylureas which on being condensed with chloroacetic acid in anhydrous pyridine, provided the desired 1-substituted thiadiazolyl-3-arylsulphonylhydantoins.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Amino-5-aryl/alkyl-1,3, 4-thiadiazoles were prepared as described earlier¹⁰.

2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole was prepared according to King and Hlavacek¹².

Arylsulphonyl Chlorides.—4-Chloro- and 4-methyl- phenylsulphonyl chlorides were obtained by chlorosulphonation of chlorobenzene and toluene, respectively, by following the method of Huntress and Carten¹³.

Arylsulphonamides.—The sulphonyl chlorides obtained above were converted into corresponding sulphonamides by the method of Huntress and Carten¹³.

1, 3-Bis-(5'-aryl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)ureas.—A mixture of urea (1 M) and hydrochloride salt of the appropriate 2-amino-5-aryl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole (2 M) was refluxed in ethanol for 3 to 4 hr. After removing about half of the solvent, diluting with a little water and cooling, a solid was obtained. This was washed well with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table I.

1-(5'-Aryl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)-3-arylureas.—An appropriate arylurea (1M) was treated with hydrochloride salt of 2-amino-5-aryl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole (1M) as above and the products were isolated as described. These are recorded in Table II.

10. Giri and Singh, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 295.

11. Das Gupta, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 417.

12. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3732.

13. *Ibid.*, 1940, 62, 511.

TABLE I

Ar.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.
4-Nitrophenyl	198°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	23.78	23.83
3-Nitrophenyl	120°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	24.10	23.83
2-Nitrophenyl	160-82°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	23.86	23.83
4-Chlorophenyl	132°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ON ₆ Cl ₂ S ₂	18.24	18.71

TABLE II

Ar ₂ .	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.
I. Ar ₁ = 3-Nitrophenyl.				
4-Phenylthiazol-2-yl	118°	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	19.42	19.81
5-Methylthiadiazol-2-yl	98°	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	26.36	26.99
Phenyl	105°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₅ S	20.26	20.52
II. Ar ₁ = 4-Nitrophenyl.				
4-Phenylthiazol-2-yl	142°	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	19.66	19.81
5-Methylthiadiazol-2-yl	301°	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ N ₇ S ₂	26.28	26.99
Phenyl	115°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₅ S	20.01	20.52
III. Ar ₁ = 4-Chlorophenyl.				
4-Phenylthiazol-2-yl	106°	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ON ₅ ClS ₂	16.18	16.92
5-Methylthiadiazol-2-yl	128°	C ₁₂ H ₉ ON ₆ ClS ₂	23.48	23.82
Phenyl	112°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ON ₄ ClS	16.44	16.94
IV. Ar ₁ = 2-Nitrophenyl.				
4-Phenylthiazol-2-yl	137°	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	19.21	19.81
V. Ar ₁ = Phenyl.				
Phenyl	100-102°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₄ S	18.32	18.91

1-Substituted Thiadiazolyl-3-arylsulphonylureas. — 4-Chlorophenyl- and 4-methylphenyl-sulphonylureas were obtained by the method of Das Gupta¹¹ by reacting the corresponding sulphonamide (1M) with potassium cyanate (1M) in anhydrous ethanol.

The appropriate arylsulphonylureas (1M) and 2-amino-5-substituted thiadiazole hydrochloride (1M) were refluxed together in anhydrous ethanol for 6 to 8 hr. After removing the solvent, the products were isolated as usual. The compounds are recorded in Table III,

1-Substituted Thiadiazolyl-3-arylsulphonylhydantoin.—A suspension of monochloroacetic acid (0.1M) and the appropriate sulphonylurea (0.1M) in anhydrous pyridine (15 ml) was gently refluxed for 30 min. and then cooled. The viscous product, thus obtained, when refluxed with anhydrous ethanol (25 ml) and cooled, furnished crystalline sulphonylhydantoin. It was recrystallised from methanol (Table IV).

TABLE III

1-(5'-Aryl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-yl)-3-arylsulphonylureas.

Ar.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found	Reqd.
I. Ar ₂ = 4-Chlorophenyl.				
4-Chlorophenyl	145	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S ₂	14.24	14.91
4-Nitrophenyl	280-81°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₅ ClS ₂	14.27	14.56
II. Ar ₂ = 4-Methylphenyl.				
4-Chlorophenyl	149°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ ClS ₂	15.42	15.66
4-Nitrophenyl	185°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	15.38	15.27
3-Nitrophenyl	285°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	15.60	15.27
2-Nitrophenyl	128-30°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	15.02	15.27
Phenyl	125°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	17.34	17.11
4-Fluorophenyl	120°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ FS ₂	16.51	16.32
4-Hydroxyphenyl	105°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	16.49	16.41

TABLE IV

Ar ₁ .	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Ar ₂ = <i>p</i> -Tolyl.						
4-Fluorophenyl	290°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄ FS ₂	12.82	12.96	14.88	14.81
4-Chlorophenyl	140°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₄ ClS ₂	12.32	12.48	14.21	14.27
4-Nitrophenyl	157°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	14.66	15.25	14.04	13.94
3-Nitrophenyl	165°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	14.54	15.25	13.98	13.94
Phenyl	100-102°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	13.76	13.52	15.17	15.45

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